

Knowledge Sharing Among Employees for Service Provision in the Hotel Industry in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: This study investigated the knowledge sharing among employees for service provision in the hotel industry in Kano State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of the study, two objectives were formulated; to identify the types of knowledge shared in the hotel industry in Kano State and to find out the services provided by the hotel industry.

Method: The study adopted quantitative research method using survey research design. The data were collected using validated questionnaire and were analyzed using frequency and percentages. The population of the study comprised 179 hotel employees from ten big hotels in Kano State.

Findings /Results: The study found out that the two major forms of knowledge tacit and explicit are both often shared among employees in the hotels industry in Kano State. The study also found out that accommodation, laundry, meetings, conferences and event planning, wellness and fitness services and car rental are some of the services provided by the hotels.

Conclusion: The study concluded that although the hotel employees do often share knowledge but mostly they do that at an informal level and does not generally understand the significance of sharing their knowledge which if emphasized will go a long way in ensuring better flow of knowledge and improved service provision.

Recommendations: The researcher thus recommends that the hotels management should enlighten their employee on the general benefits of knowledge sharing in their services interactions, the management should also ensure a periodic investigation on

knowledge sharing practices. Lastly the hotels management should also have the best practices modalities through good reward mechanism, good leadership, trust and incorporate knowledge friendly culture that promote knowledge sharing and motivate the employees to share knowledge in the industry.

Keywords: Knowledge sharing, Service provision, Hotel industry

Introduction

Knowledge sharing is an activity through which knowledge, including experiences, information, skills, or expertise is exchanged, shared, and transferred among organizational members. Knowledge sharing is not a simple process of sharing knowledge; rather, organizational members adjust their beliefs and actions through intense social interactions. To support the above statement, Cleveland and Ellis (2015) and Phung, Hawryszkiewycz and Binsawad (2016) indicated that knowledge sharing involves through participation in social interaction that guide or change the way a member thinks by making him or her aware of other member's personal insights, capturing, organizing, transferring and reusing the experiential knowledge. Hong, Suh, and Koo (2011) also point out that knowledge sharing occurs when members interact with one another by defining the problem they encountered, discussing options and sharing knowledge in which the result or byproduct of their interaction is to find a valuable solution to their problem or contribute to improve processes. Sunartaa, Rohmanb, and Kawedar (2020) conducted a study to examine the effect of KS on organizational performance with the types of innovation as mediation in three, four and five-star hotels in Bali Province, Indonesia. A total of one hundred and five (105) hotels participated in this study, based on a survey of two hundred and thirty (230) hotels. The finding shows that in managing knowledge, the value of one's knowledge will increase for the organization when shared and increases organizational performance.

This is in line with Eresia-Eke (2015) study which states knowledge sharing in an organization can create new values to improve its development, growth and organizational performance. In the hospitality industry, knowledge sharing can promote organizational innovative performance (Kim, Lee, Paek, & Lee, 2013). Similarly, Idris (2015) found out that knowledge dissemination is significantly related to competitive advantage in the hospitality industry. The researchers recommend increased knowledge dissemination via knowledge sharing and transfer among employees and between departments.

Hidayat and Lee (2018) in their survey study also submitted that the influence of knowledge sharing on the performance of service innovation showed significant results. The study also indicated that knowledge sharing activities have a positive effect on performance of restaurant business services in North Kalimantan. Similarly, in a study by Dabiri, Lasisi and Olayinka (2015), on knowledge sharing innovation and employees performance in the Nigerian hotel industry, confirms that there is a statistically significant relationship between knowledge sharing attitudes and employee's performance in the Nigerian hotel services.

Burke (2011) submitted that there are two quite distinctive, divergent and widely accepted types of knowledge tacit and explicit. The tacit knowledge is the know-how which is embedded in the mind of a person, while explicit knowledge is knowledge that is codified in documents, databases, and web pages, etc. or written down and stored on computers. The heterogeneous nature with its intangible goods and services puts special attention on the way hospitality and tourism knowledge can be managed and organize (Batra, 2022). The bureau of statistics (2015) on the review of the Nigerian accommodation and food services sector based on the rebased GDP, the accommodation and food sector stated that the industry contributed about 0,45% of the nation's total value of goods services in 2010. Gross earnings for the accommodation sector in Nigeria totaled at N638, 978.08 million in 2010, which increased by N44, 888.41 million or 7.03% to N683, 866.49 million in 2011 and by N46, 238.21 million or 6.76% to reach N730, 104.70 million in 2012.

Statement of the Problem

Knowledge sharing among employees, with the customers and with the business partners has a tremendous potential pay-off in ensuring improved customer service, shorter delivery-cycle times and increased collaboration within the hotel and with the business partners. Knowledge sharing help hotels to transfer, share and save knowledge within the hotels and it also support staff in their service interactions.

Regrettable, despite the numerous benefits of knowledge sharing in any contemporary organizations including hotel industry in terms of enabling employees to generate and implement new ideas for gaining competitive advantage, previous studies have indicated that hotel industry demonstrated slow adoption of this concept and practice. For example, Ozigbo (2015) conducted a study on knowledge management implementation in Nigerian hospitality industry and the findings revealed that there is lack of awareness of knowledge

management framework and its implementation in the industry. Because of the lack of awareness the employees did not know how to help in other to improve the knowledge sharing in the industry. Similarly, Hallin and Marnburg (2008) conducted a review on empirical research of KM in the hospitality industry and they identified that, overall, the research on knowledge processes in the sector is scarce and weak.

Hotel industry plays an important role in economic development by sustaining employment and income from the industry, benefits individuals, businesses and governments in all economies including Nigeria. This study will shed light on the types of knowledge shared among employees in the hotel industry and the services provided. The study will give a practical contribution as a tool for innovation and having competitive advantage in the hotel industry. It will also make the hospitality enterprises act as intelligently as possible to secure its viability and overall success and to also realize the best value of its knowledge assets. The hotel industry could drive the benefit of the results of the study because of the specific features of this industry such as the special features of services provision to customers, which depends strongly on the ability of hotels to acquire, to develop, to accumulate and to distribute knowledge assets in the provision of the right service that will ensure customers satisfaction.

Research Objectives

1. To identify the types of knowledge shared among employees in the hotel industry in Kano State.
2. To find out the services provided by the hotel industry.

Literature Review

Types of knowledge shared

There are many ways in which knowledge is categorized, knowledge can be categorized into individual and collective knowledge, old and new knowledge or declarative and procedural knowledge etc., but the most notable, and major classification of knowledge are two kinds of knowledge: tacit(embodied) and explicit(codified), explicit knowledge is knowledge that can be documented, categorized, transmitted to others as information, and illustrated to others as through demonstrations, explanations and other forms of sharing, by contrast tacit knowledge is knowledge which draws from the accumulated

experience and learning of a person and which is hard to reproduce or share with others. (Bollinger & smith, 2011).

Similarly, in the context of hotels and knowledge management, the key types of knowledge are explicit, implicit, and tacit, with explicit knowledge being documented and easily shared, while implicit and tacit knowledge reside in individual experience and practice. In the hotel industry, shared knowledge encompasses task-specific skills, tacit knowledge (learned through experience), customer-related insights, network connections, and market trends, all crucial for providing excellent service and maintaining a competitive edge.

Bouncken (2002) categorizes hotel specific knowledge as this knowledge stated in sources as task- specific, task-related, transactive memory and guest-related knowledge for hotels. And also recommended that hoteliers should always seek, use and value knowledge like professionals in other business sectors. Task-specific knowledge; includes the practical skills and procedures necessary for specific roles, like preparing a cocktail, setting a table, or checking in a guest. Task related knowledge; contains individuals' shared knowledge not of a single task, but of related tasks, e.g. the form of teamwork in the firm.

Transactive memory; includes decentralized knowledge of the other organizational members' cognitive models. The main understanding of this form of knowledge category is the realization of each other's knowledge, preferences, weaknesses, and work values. Guest-related knowledge; involves understanding customer behavior, preferences, and needs, as well as effective communication and service skills. Tacit knowledge; refers to the knowledge and skills that are difficult to articulate or document, often learned through observation, practice, and experience. Examples include understanding customer preferences or anticipating their needs. Network-related knowledge; this encompasses understanding the industry's network, including relationships with suppliers, other businesses, and industry professionals. Market-related knowledge; this includes understanding market trends, competitor activities, and promotional strategies.

Services Provided by Hotels

Service consists of a set of activities more or less intangible which naturally occurs in interactions between customers and staff, physical resources, goods and or service

providers systems that will be solutions to customer problems The hotel industry provides a wide array of services, including accommodation, food and beverage, recreational facilities, and various amenities to cater to guests' needs and enhance their stay. Many hotels offer different services for different guests with different needs, such as fitness gyms, laundry, food/catering, beverages, recreation, travel guide, tourism, airport shuttle, meetings/event planning, entertainment, sports, saunas, nursing care etc. Moreover, as the competition becomes keener, hotels are daily coming out with new tricks to stay ahead of competitors, while some provide complimentary breakfast, others provide free internet service, daily complimentary newspaper, cosmetic bags which include toothbrush, soap, hand cream etc.

Batinić (2016) stated that the breadth of the range of hotel services, is conditioned by the category of the hotel facility, the size of the hotel facility, hotel location, weather aspect of the hotel business, complexity of hotel organizational structure and business policy in the market. The author further classified hotels services into: Accommodation services - provided in the hotel accommodation units - apartments and rooms; Food and beverage services - depending on the type and category of the hotel, provided in hotel dining rooms, banquet halls, lounges, breakfast rooms,, grill-rooms, coffee shops, cocktail bars, guests can also be served in their rooms (room service) Recreation and sport services- guest have access to pools, tennis courts and golf courses, various types of courts, gyms, bowling alley, walking and jogging paths, and various events can be organized.

Cultural - entertainment services - hotels often organize concerts of classical music, or host popular artists, exhibitions, have a library, conference facilities for fun and games, especially during bad weather, guests are offered specially prepared entertainment programs (animation). Merchant services - guests are offered the opportunity to buy souvenirs, newspapers, various personal necessities, up to high fashion boutiques and the like. Trades services - hotel facilities often offer hairdressing, beauticians and nail salons, photographers, watchmakers and others; health and other services - hotels offer guests the possibility of diagnosis, treatment, rehabilitation and other.

Similarly, Bardis (2012) conducted a study titled “strategic management in hotel, in Corfu Island Greece” the researcher discovered that the hotel’s main business idea is the provision of accommodation to the customers but it also has a wide range of other services, too; restaurant, fitness center, spa, sports, entertainment, hairdresser, conference facilities. Djordjevic, Zecevic & Branislava (2016) conducted an empirical survey study on a sample of eight hundred and fifty (850) respondents in Serbia the study

found that hotel's comfort, convenience and location are the most important in choosing the hotel facility.

Methodology:

This study employed a cross sectional survey design, which is suitable for collecting data at a specific point in time to examine the current state knowledge sharing and its predictors among employees in the hotel industry in Kano State Nigeria. The design enables the systematic collection and analysis of data from diverse and representative sample to address the research objectives effectively.

The population of the study comprised 179 employees from ten big hotels in Kano State. These are Babale suites, Bristol Guest Hotel, Bon Hotel Kano, Grand Central Hotel, Chilla Luxury Suites, Ni'imah Guest Palace, Porto Golf Hotel, Prince Hotel, Nasarawa Guest House, and Tahir Guest Palace. The researcher did not use any sampling technique because the size of the population is considered manageable, therefore all the 179 hotel employees were used as the sample size of the study.

Structured questionnaire was used as the primary data collection instrument. The questionnaire was designed to capture the relevant information on types of knowledge shared and services provision by the hotel in the industry. It consists of both closed-ended and open-ended questions to facilitate comprehensive data collection. The instrument was validated through expert review and pilot-tested to ensure clarity, reliability, and relevance to the study objectives.

The questionnaires were administered physically to the 179 hotel employees across the ten hotels. Adequate follow-ups were conducted to maximize the response rate. Out of the 179 distributed questionnaires 136 were completed and deemed valid for analysis, representing 75% response rate. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies, percentages, and mean scores, were used to summarize and describe the findings of the study.

Results:

Table 1: Types of Knowledge Shared among Hotel Employees

S/N	Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD
1	I share knowledge generated from hospitality books and journals(explicit)	57(41.9)	62(45.6)	8(5.9)	8(5.9)	1(.7)
2	I share knowledge generated from hotel databases(explicit)	32(23.5)	64(47.1)	24(17.6)	14(17.6)	2(10.3)
3	I share knowledge generated from internal memos(explicit)	38(27.9)	64(47.1)	19(14.0)	12(8.8)	3(2.2)
4	I share knowledge generated from online training(explicit)	36(26.5)	70(51.5)	16(11.8)	10(7.4)	42.9)
5	I share knowledge generated from conference and seminars(explicit)	44(32.4)	66(48.5)	18(13.2)	5(3.7)	3(2.2)
6	I share knowledge generated from exhibitions(explicit)	24(17.6)	60(44.1)	26(19.1)	22(16.2)	4(2.9)
7	I share knowledge on routines and activities within the hotel(tacit)	53(39.0)	56(41.2)	15(11.0)	12(8.8)	3(2.2)
8	I share knowledge on customers suggestions and complains(tacit)	52(38.2)	61(44.9)	10(7.4)	11(8.1)	2(1.5)
9	I share experience generated from colleagues(tacit)	41(30.1)	66(48.5)	16(11.8)	12(8.8)	1(.7)
10	I share experience generated from customers/guest(tacit)	42(30.9)	66(48.5)	13(9.6)	14(10.3)	1(.7)

Source: Field Survey, 2019

The findings of the study revealed that the majority 70 (51.5%) of the respondents agreed that they share knowledge generated from online trainings, while 16 (11.8%) were undecided and 14 (10.3%) did not agree with the statement. About 66 (48.5%) of the respondents equally agreed that they share knowledge generated from conference, seminars, experience generated from colleagues and experience generated from

customers/guest, while 18(13.2%) of the respondents were undecided and 14(10.3%) did not agree with the statements.

Also the findings indicate that 64(47.1%) of the respondents agreed that they share knowledge generated from hotel databases and knowledge generated from internal memos while 24(17.6%) were undecided and 14(17.6%) did not agree with the statement. About 62(45.6%) of the respondents agreed that they do share knowledge generated from hospitality books and journals while 8(5.9%) were undecided and did not agree with the statement. With regards to sharing knowledge on customers suggestions and complains 61(44.9%) of the respondents agreed while 11(8.1%) did not agree and 10(7.4%) were undecided with the statement.

The result of the findings similarly revealed that about 60(44.1%) of the respondents agreed that they share knowledge generated from exhibitions while 26(19.1%) were undecided and about 22(16.2%) did not agree with the statement. Also, with regards to sharing knowledge on routines and activities within the hotel the findings shows that about 56(41.2%) of the respondents do agreed with the statement but 15(11.0%) were undecided and 12(8.8%) of the respondents were not in agreement with the statement. The above findings indicated that hotel employees in Kano State do share both tacit and explicit knowledge in their daily activities in the hotel.

Table 2: Frequency of Knowledge Sharing among Hotel Employees

S/N	Frequency of knowledge sharing	Frequency	Percentage
1	Most Often	34	25.0
2	Often	70	51.5
3	Not Often	12	8.8
4	Occasionally	20	14.7
	Total	136	100.0

Source: Generated from SPSS 26.0,2019

Table 2 indicates the extent of knowledge sharing in which the majority 70(51.5%) of them responded that they often share knowledge, While 20(14.7%) of them responded that they

occasionally share knowledge. Thus, the majority of the hotel employees in Kano State were found often sharing knowledge.

Table 3: Services Provided by the Hotels Industry

S/N	Services in the hotel industry	Frequency/percentage	
		Yes	No
1	Accommodation service	135(99.3)	1(.7)
2	Food, beverages and catering services	134(98.5)	2(1.5)
3	Wellness and fitness services	87(64.0)	49(36.0)
4	Meetings, conferences, and event planning services	124(92.2)	12(8.8)
5	ICT/Internet services	97(71.3)	39(28.7)
6	Laundry services	132(97.1)	4(2.9)
7	First aid services	87(64.0)	49(36.0)
8	Travelling services	63(46.3)	73(53.7)
9	Car rental services	106(77.9)	30(22.1)

Sources: Generated from SPSS 26.0, 2019

Table 3 above indicated that the highest number of the respondents 135(99.3%) responded that accommodation services was provided by the their hotel, followed by 134(98.5%) of the respondents who indicated that food, beverages and catering services are provided by their hotels, followed by 132(97.1%) who also indicated that laundry services was provided by their hotels, this is followed by 124(92.2%) of the respondent who responded that meetings, conferences and event planning services was also provided by their hotels while 12(8.8%), 4(2.9%), 2(1.5%) and 1(.7%) of the respondents did not respond on the said services to being provided by their hotels. The findings revealed that accommodation services, food beverages and catering services, laundry services and meeting/event planning services are the main services rendered in the majority of hotels in Kano State.

Further, the findings indicated that the majority 106(77.9%), 97(71.3%), and 87(64.0%) of the respondents responded that car rental services, ICT/Internet services, wellness and fitness services, first aid services are services provided by their hotel industry, while 30(22.1%), 49(36.0), 30(22.1%) and 39(28.7) did not respondent on the above services being provided by their hotel industry. On regards to travelling services the table also indicated that about 73(53.7%) of the respondents did not respond, while 63(46.3%) of

the respondents do respond on the said services as being provided by their hotel. Thus, this indicated that travelling services, ICT/internet services, wellness and fitness services, first aid services are provided but not by all the hotels in Kano State.

Conclusion:

Based on the finding of the study hotel employees in Kano State do often share both tacit and explicit knowledge but lack the formal standard in doing that. However, there is room for improvement in the depth and frequency of knowledge sharing. To ensure effective service provision in the hotel industry, there is need for a more deliberate efforts to encourage knowledge sharing among the employees for the benefits of others and better service provision and this could be achieved through various rewards mechanisms which will motivate the employees to share their knowledge.

Recommendations:

1. The researcher recommends that hotel employees should be made to understand the general concept of knowledge, types of knowledge, knowledge sharing, knowledge sharing strategies, factors facilitating it, tools used for knowledge sharing, inhibitors associated to knowledge sharing and the benefits associated to knowledge sharing by an expert in the field of knowledge management as this will help in their service interactions in the industry.
2. The researcher recommends that the hotel managements should have a best-practices modalities through good reward mechanisms, good leadership, trust, and incorporate knowledge friendly culture that promotes knowledge sharing, and also high levels of performance-based pay system which will motivate employees to share knowledge in the hotel industry.
3. There is the need by the hotel management to include other services such as recreational and sport, cultural-entertainment, tourism, trades, hairdressing, beauticians and nail salons, photography services, others are health related such as diagnosis, treatment, rehabilitation services. These services can give the hotel an edge over their competitors and ensured returned customers if provided effectively.

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